

STUDIES ON THE FRIES REARRANGEMENT

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Fries rearrangement has been studied in the case of eight new esters of 4-ethylphenol at two different temperatures. The *ortho*-hydroxy ketones thus obtained have been characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

Auwers and Mauss (*Annalen*, 1928, 480, 240) obtained a 70 % yield of 2-hydroxy-5-ethylacetophenone by the Fries rearrangement of 4-ethyl phenylacetate. This reaction has been extended in this paper to eight new esters of 4-ethylphenol, viz., propionate, butyrate, caproate, heptate, caprylate, caprate, laurate and myristate, which were obtained in the usual manner by the action of the acid chlorides on 4-ethylphenol. The reaction was studied at two different temperatures, viz., 100° and 130°; an *o*-hydroxy ketone was obtained in each case and the difference in the yield of ketone formed at two temperatures was very small, the reaction being a little more rapid at 130°.

EXPERIMENTAL

The esters were obtained by the action of the appropriate acid chloride on ethylphenol. The general method followed is outlined below.

4-Ethylphenol (0.1M) was taken in a 250 c.c. r.b. flask fitted with a reflux condenser carrying a calcium chloride tube and the appropriate acid chloride (0.11M) was added slowly to it. The reaction mixture was warmed on the water-bath until the evolution of hydrogen chloride had ceased. After cooling, the mixture was extracted with ether, washed with 1% caustic soda, then with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate; the ether was distilled off and the residue distilled under reduced pressure.

TABLE I

4 Ethyl phenyl esters	Reactants		Yield of esters.	B.P.	Molecular formula	Analysis			
	Phenol.	Acid chloride.				Found C	Found H.	Calc C.	Calc H.
Propionate	7.07g	5.9g	6.5g. 63.2%	130°/15mm	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ O ₂	74.30%	7.85%	74.15%	7.86%
Butyrate	9	8.7	8.5 60.1	150°/9	C ₁₂ H ₁₆ O ₂	74.81	8.72	74.91	8.90
Caproate	11	13.3	13 65.85	166°/9	C ₁₄ H ₂₀ O ₂	76.50	9.20	76.37	9.09
Heptate	10	13.4	13 67.7	178°/11	C ₁₅ H ₂₂ O ₂	77.20	9.20	76.93	9.40
Caprylate	10	14.7	10.5 50.16	195°/12	C ₁₆ H ₂₄ O ₂	77.31	9.40	77.76	9.67
Caprate	5.05	8.3	8 70.1	226°/19	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O ₂	78.45	10.40	78.27	10.14
Laurate	6.1	12	12.5 82.2	210°/16	C ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₂	78.67	10.29	78.94	10.52
Myristate	6.8	15	14.6 78.9	210°/14	C ₂₂ H ₃₆ O ₂	78.80	10.80	79.52	10.84

TABLE II
Fries rearrangement

4-Ethylphenyl esters.	Ester.	AlCl ₃ .	Temp.	Ketone formed. R=2-hydroxy-5-ethylphenyl; K=ketone.	Yield.	B. p.	Analysis of ketone		M. p.	Mol. formula.	Dinitrophenyl hydrazone			
							Found, %C	%H			Calc. %C	%H	Found, %N	Calc.
Propionate	3.0 g.	3-7 g.	100° 130°	R-ethyl-K	4.18 1.8	115°/10mm.	74.20	7.71	74.15	7.86	200°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ O ₅ N ₄	15.43	15.64
Butyrate	4.0	4-5	100° 130°	R-butyl-K	3.0 2.8	145°/10	74.70	8.90	74.91	8.90	184°	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ O ₅ N ₄	14.80	15.00
Caproate	4.0	4.0	100° 130°	R-n-amy1-K	3.3 3.2	162°/10	76.52	9.22	76.37	9.09	178°	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₄	13.77	14.00
Heptoate	4.0	3.9	100° 130°	R-γ-hexyl-K	3.2 3.0	178°/9	77.10	9.31	76.93	9.40	129°	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ O ₅ N ₄	13.20	13.53
Caprylate	4.0	3.5	100° 130°	R-η-heptyl-K	3.2 3.1	184°/11	77.41	9.30	77.76	9.67	122°	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₅ N ₄	12.87	13.08
Caprate	3.0	2.4	100° 130°	R-n-nonyl-K	2.3 2.2	162°/11	78.35	10.30	78.27	10.14	115°	C ₂₄ H ₂₆ O ₅ N ₄	12.23	12.28
Laurate	4.5	3.3	100° 130°	R-lauryl-K	3.1 2.9	210°/19	78.77	10.40	78.94	10.54	75°	C ₂₆ H ₃₆ O ₅ N ₄	11.18	11.50
Myristate	5.0	3.3	100° 130°	R-myristyl-K	3.3 3.0	210°/17	79.70	10.70	79.52	10.84	66°	C ₂₈ H ₄₀ O ₅ N ₄	10.60	10.93

The molecular weights of the ketones are the same as that of the respective esters from which they have been prepared by the Fries rearrangement.

Fries Rearrangement of the Esters

The Fries rearrangement was studied at two temperatures (100° and 130°). The general procedure followed is given below.

Finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.1M) was taken in a 125 c.c. r.b. flask fitted with a reflux condenser carrying a dropping funnel and a calcium chloride tube, and the ester (0.06M) was gradually added to it. The temperature was gradually raised to 100° in one experiment (water-bath) and to 130° in the other (oil-bath). The evolution of hydrogen chloride commenced at 60° . The reaction was slightly more rapid at 130° . After two hours the reaction mixture was cooled and dilute hydrochloric acid was added to the red puffy mass obtained to decompose the aluminium complex. The oil that separated was taken up in ether, washed successively with water, 1% sodium carbonate solution and then again with water. After dehydration over anhydrous sodium sulphate the ether was distilled off and the residue distilled under reduced pressure.

The distillate gave an intense red-violet colour with ferric chloride and on addition of dilute caustic soda a yellowish red precipitate was obtained. It thus conforms to Pyman's tests for *ortho*-hydroxy ketones (Pyman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930,280) The *o*-hydroxy ketones thus obtained were converted into their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones which were recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. The yield of ketones at 130° is a little lower than at 100° .

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